

Trends and patterns of Infant Mortality Rates in India

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Abstract

This paper examines the trends and magnitude of Infant Mortality Rates (IMR) in India. The result shows that though the trend declined, it has not decreased to the level as expected. Millennium Development Goal (MDG) for India was reduce IMR to 28 by 2015. As per the latest Sample Registration System (SRS) report (published in May, 2019) IMR reached 33 in India, ie near to the MDG for the year 2017. The same estimate shows that in rural area it is 37 and in urban area 23. In India in urban area IMR has reached the millennium development goal but still rural areas are lagging behind. Among the states 6 union territories and 18 states have achieved MDG by 2017. Five states have IMR above 40 in 2017.

Infant Mortality Rate is a useful indicator of a country's level of health or development, and is a component of the physical quality of life index. Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) is the number of deaths of infants under one year old in a given year per 1,000 live births. Infant mortality rate thus indicates the number of deaths of babies under one year of age per 1,000 live births in the same year. The rate in a given region, therefore, is the total number of newborns dying under one year of age divided by the total number of live births during the year, then all multiplied by 1,000. The infant mortality rate is also called the infant death rate (per 1,000 live births). The method of calculating IMR often varies widely between countries, and is based on how they define a live birth and how many premature infants are born in the country. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines a live birth as any born human being who demonstrates independent signs of life, including breathing, voluntary muscle movement, or heartbeat. Many countries, however, including certain European states and Japan, only count as live births cases where an infant breathes at birth, which makes their reported IMR numbers somewhat lower and raises their rates of perinatal mortality.. As World Health Organization, annual infant death have declined to 4.1 million in 2017 from 8.8 million in 1990. IMR is often used as an indicator of the level of health in a country and as a barometer of overall welfare of a community or country.

Infant mortality rate comprises of two parts, ie Neo-natal mortality rate and Post neo-natal mortality rate. The neo-natal mortality rate also comprises of two parts they are early neo-natal mortality rate and late neo-natal mortality rate. Neo-natal mortality rate (NMR) is the number of infant deaths of less than 29 days during the

year. Late neo-natal mortality rate is number of infant deaths of 7 days to less than 29 days during the year. Early neo-natal mortality rate *is the* number of infant deaths of less than 7 days during the year . Perinatal mortality includes deaths between the foetal viability (22 weeks gestation) and the end of the 7th day after delivery. Post neonatal mortality only includes deaths after 28 days of life but before one year. In India Sample Registration System (SRS) is designed for reliable estimates of fertility and mortality indicators at State and National level separately for rural and urban areas. This is the main source for fertility and mortality data since 1969-70

Table.1
Definition of the infant mortality rate

Infant mortality rate (IMR)	$\frac{\text{Number of infant deaths during the year}}{\text{Number of live births during the year}} \times 1000$
Neo-natal mortality rate (NMR)	$\frac{\text{Number of infant deaths of less than 29 days during the year}}{\text{Number of live births during the year}} \times 1000$
Early neo-natal mortality rate	$\frac{\text{Number of infant deaths of less than 7 days during the year}}{\text{Number of live births during the year}} \times 1000$
Late neo-natal mortality rate	$\frac{\text{Number of infant deaths of 7 days to less than 29 days during the year}}{\text{Number of live births during the year}} \times 1000$
Post neo-natal mortality rate (PNMR)	$\frac{\text{Number of infant deaths of 29 days to less than one year during the year}}{\text{Number of live births during the year}} \times 1000$
Peri-natal mortality Rate (PMR)	$\frac{\text{Number of still births and infant deaths of less than 7 days during the year}}{\text{Number of live births and still births during the year}} \times 1000$

Data source

The major objective of the study is to examine the trends and pattern of infant mortality rate in India. This paper gives an updated analysis of magnitude of infant mortality in India. The study examines the year wise, area wise, gender wise and state wise trends in IMR in India The study used the data from Sample Registration System (SRS) provided through various issues of SRS bulletins.

Millennium Development Goal and IMR

MDGs are a set of numerical & time-bound targets to measure achievements in human and social development laid down by the UN .In September 2000, leaders from 189 nations agreed on a vision for the future: a world with less poverty, hunger and disease, greater survival prospects for mothers and their infants, better educated children, equal opportunities for women, and a healthier environment; a world in which developed and developing countries worked in partnership for the betterment of all. This vision took the shape of eight Millennium Development Goals, which provide a framework of time-bound targets by which progress can be measured. MDG includes eight goals like eradicate poverty and hunger, universal primary education, promote gender equality and women empowerment, reduce child mortality, improve maternal health, combat HIV/AIDS, malaria and other diseases, ensure environmental sustainability, and develop a global partnership for development. he targets of India was to achieve by 2015 maternal health Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) to 109, reduce infant mortality Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) to 28 and reduce child mortality Under 5 Mortality Rate (U5MR) to 42.

World level infant mortality rate

Table.2 shows the IMR at world level. During 1950-55 the rate was as high as 152 and due to the development efforts it reduced to 47 and is expected to reach 23 by 2045- 2050. There was a significant reduction in the IMR at the world level.

Table 2
World Infant Mortality Rate-1950-2050

Years	Rate	Years	Rate
1950–1955	152	2000–2005	52
1955–1960	136	2005–2010	47
1960–1965	116	2010–2015	43
1965–1970	100	2015–2020	40
1970–1975	91	2020–2025	37
1975–1980	83	2025–2030	34
1980–1985	74	2030–2035	31
1985–1990	65	2035–2040	28
1990–1995	61	2040–2045	25
1995–2000	57	2045–2050	23

Source: UN report

IMR in India

Infant mortality rate in India since 1981 is shown in the Table.3. In 1981 the IMR was 110 and declined 30 point by 1991 and reached to 80. It further declined by 14 point by 2001. In 2011 India it reached the level of 44. IMR was further declined to 33 in 2017.

Table.3
Infant Mortality Rate in India-1981-2017

Year	IMR	Year	IMR
1981	110		
1991	80	2006	57
1995	74	2007	55
1996	72	2008	53
1997	71	2009	50
1998	72	2010	47
1999	70	2011	44
2000	68	2012	42
2001	66	2013	40
2002	63	2014	39
2003	60	2015	37
2004	58	2016	34
2005	58	2017	33

Source: Sample Registration system (SRS bulletin)various issues

Table 4 gives neonatal mortality and infant mortality rate in India as per National Family Health Survey (NFHS) reports. In the first report IMR was 78.5 and shows that it declined to 57 by 2005-06, ie in the NFHS-III. The estimate was more or less similar to the SRS report. As per NFHS- 2015-16 reports the infant mortality rate is 41.

Table.4
Neo-Natal Mortality and Infant Mortality Rate in India as per NFHS reports

Indicators	Under five mortality rate	Infant Mortality Rate
NFHS-1 (1992-93)	109	78.5
NFHS-II (1998-99)	95	67.6
NFHS-III 2005-06	74	57.0
NFHS-IV- 2015-16	50	41

Source: NFHS Reports (Various issues)

Infant Mortality Rate –rural and urban differences

In India the IMR is very high in rural areas and it is above national level in all years since 1972 as per the Table.5. In 1972 the rural IMR rate was 150 and Urban rate was 85. The IMR rate shows a declining trend in India. In 2017 the rate was 37 and 23 respectively in rural and urban area. The urban area has achieved the target of MDGs

by 2012. There exists a clear disparity between rural and urban area in the case of infant mortality rate. It is higher in the rural area,

Table.5
Infant Mortality Rate –rural urban differences

Year	Total	Rural	Urban	Year	Total	Rural	Urban	Year	Total	Rural	Urban
1972	139	150	85	1988	94	102	62	2003	60	66	38
1973	134	143	89	1989	91	98	58	2004	58	64	40
1974	126	136	74	1990	80	86	50	2005	58	64	40
1975	140	151	84	1991	80	87	53	2006	57	62	39
1976	129	139	80	1992	79	85	53	2007	55	61	37
1978	127	137	74	1993	74	82	45	2008	53	58	36
1979	120	130	72	1994	74	80	52	2009	50	55	34
1980	114	124	65	1995	74	80	48	2010	47	51	31
1981	110	119	62	1996	72	77	46	2011	44	48	29
1982	105	114	65	1997	71	77	45	2012	42	46	28
1983	105	114	66	1998	72	77	45	2013	40	44	27
1984	104	113	66	1999	70	75	44	2014	39	43	26
1985	97	107	59	2000	68	74	44	2015	37	41	25
1986	96	105	62	2001	66	72	42	2016	34	38	23
1987	95	104	61	2002	63	69	40	2017	33	37	23

Source: Sample Registration system (SRS bulletin) various issues

Indicators of infant mortality rate

Various components of infant mortality rates are given in the Table. 6. Neonatal mortality rate, mortality rate less than 29 days has considerably decreased in India. In 1971 it was 75.2 and decreased to 25 in 2015. Both in the rural and urban area also the similar trend exists. But in the rural area it is still higher compared to urban area. Post natal mortality rate, PNMR, ie mortality rate 29 to less than one year, also declined considerably since 1971. It reached to 19 in 2015 from 54.5 in 1971. PNMR is also higher in rural area than in the urban area, peri natal mortality rate, PMR ie mortality rate less than 7 days is high in India. In 1971 it was 53.4 and decreased to 31.9 only in 2015. Rate of still birth also shows a declining trend in India since 1971 as shown in the table.

Table.6
Components of Infant mortality rate by residence from 1971 to 2015

Year	Infant mortality rate			Neo-natal mortality rate			Post-natal mortality rate			Peri-natal mortality rate			Still Birth rate		
	Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban
1971	129	138	82	75.2	80.6	45.4	54.2	57.4	36.6	53.4	56.7	35.6	17.5	18.3	12.9
1975	140	151	84	78.3	84.3	46.2	62.1	66.7	37.8	55.2	58.8	36.1	17.6	18.6	12.5
1980	114	124	65	69.3	75.5	39.1	44.6	48.3	26.1	55.7	59.8	35.3	11.3	12.0	7.9
1985	97	107	59	60.1	66.6	33.3	37.1	39.9	25.6	48.1	52.4	30.4	10.4	10.8	8.9
1990	80	86	50	52.5	57.4	30.9	27.2	28.9	19.5	48.4	51.7	34.0	11.8	11.9	11.0
1995	74	80	48	48.1	52.3	29.2	25.9	27.5	19.0	44.6	47.6	31.2	9.2	9.3	8.8

2000	68	74	44	44.4	48.7	27.5	23.4	25.3	16.1	40.3	43.9	26.2	8.5	8.9	6.9
2005	58	64	40	36.7	40.5	23.2	21.7	23.1	16.7	36.7	40.3	23.7	9.1	9.4	8.1
2010	47	51	31	32.6	36.4	19.3	14.4	14.6	11.9	31.9	34.7	21.9	6.7	6.8	6.5
2015	37	41	25	25	29	15	19	22	11	23	26	15	4	4	4

Source: Sample Registration system (SRS bulletin) various issues

The infant mortality rate in rural and urban area and according to gender is given Table.7. From the table it is very clear that there exists gender gap in the rural and urban area. The IMR in urban area is lower than the rural area. In the urban area the IMR is 23 in 2017, whereas it is 37 in rural area. IMR of females in rural area in 2017 is 34 and in urban area it is 25. Compared to 1985, both in urban and rural area the IMR has improved very much after 2010. In urban area India has achieved the MDG by 2015. Whereas in rural area, India is still lagging behind.

Table.7
Gender wise IMR in rural and urban area- 1985-2017

Year	Total			Rural			Urban		
	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female
1985	97	96	98	107	106	107	59	56	62
1990	80	78	81	86	84	88	50	50	49
1995	74	73	76	80	78	82	48	49	47
2000	68	67	69	74	72	76	44	45	42
2005	58	56	61	64	62	66	40	37	43
2010	47	46	49	51	50	53	31	30	33
2015	37	35	39	41	40	43	25	23	28
2016	34	33	36	38	37	40	23	22	25
2017	33	32	34	37	36	37	23	22	25

Source: Sample Registration system (SRS bulletin) various issues

IMR in India-State wise

The state wise infant mortality rate is given in Table .8, for 1961 and 2017. The states are grouped according to the various range of mortality rate. In 1961 the lowest IMR was in the range of 31 to 40. This category included only one state, ie Manipur. Majority of the states have IMR 80 and above. Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh and Lakshadweep have highest IMR in 1961. In 2017, for which the latest data are available shows comparatively better position among male and female. Majority of the states are in the category of IMR below 30. Arunachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Assam, Meghalaya, Odisha and Uttar Pradesh have the highest IMR.

Table.8
State wise and Gender wise infant mortality rate in India

	1961		2017	
	Male	Female	Male	Female
0-10			Kerala, Goa, Nagaland, Sikkim, Puducherry	Kerala, Goa Chandigarh
11-20			Delhi, Maharashtra Punjab, Tamilnadu, Manipur, Mizoram, Andaman and Nicobar Island, Chandigarh, Dadra and Nagar Haveli Daman& Diu	Delhi,, Maharashtra Tamilnadu, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Andaman and Nicobar Island, Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Daman& Diu, Lakshadweep, Puducherry
21-30			Gujarat, Haryana, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Telangana, West	Gujarat, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Punjab, Telangana

			Bengal, Himachal Pradesh, Tripura, Lakshadweep	Uttarakhand, West Bengal, Himachal Pradesh, Tripura
31-40	Manipur	Manipur	Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Jharkhand, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand	Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Haryana, Jharkhand, Rajasthan
41-50		Kerala	Assam, Madhya Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya	Assam, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha, Uttar Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya
51-60	Chandigarh, Kerala, Daman & Diu, Goa	Chandigarh, Daman & Diu, Goa, West Bengal, Nagaland		
61-70	Delhi	Mizoram, Andaman & Nicobar, Puducherry, Delhi		
71-80	Mizoram, Punjab, Nagaland, Puducherry, Andaman & Nicobar, Jammu & Kashmir	Karnataka, Meghalaya, Jammu & Kashmir, Punjab		
81-90	Gujarat, Meghalaya, Haryana, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu	Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Gujarat, Sikkim, Lakshadweep, Himachal Pradesh, Maharashtra		
91-100	Bihar, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh	D & Nagar Haveli, Bihar		
101-110	Himachal Pradesh, D & Nagar Haveli, West Bengal, Sikkim, Tripura			
111-120	Rajasthan, Orissa	Arunachal Pradesh, Orissa, Rajasthan, Tripura, Haryana		
121 and above	Lakshadweep, Uttar Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh	Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh		

Source: Compiled from Sample Registration system (SRS bulletin) various issues

Conclusions

Infant Mortality Rate in India shows a decline and we have almost reached the millennium development goal of 28. While the IMR national average is 33, it stands at 37 in the rural areas and 23 in the urban regions. However, neo-natal deaths continue to be a challenge where 25 babies are still dying for every 1,000 born. Gender differences in infant mortality rate has been reduced. Infant mortality rate was 34 and 32 among females and males in India in 2017. The rural urban difference is high in India. It is 37 and 23 for rural and urban areas respectively. The state wise analysis shows that it was decreased considerably. Some of the states like Kerala, Goa, Nagaland, Sikkim and Puducherry shows a better performance. Still states like Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Meghalaya, Odisha and Uttar Pradesh have high infant mortality rate. These states have IMR above 40 in 2017. There was a significant improvement in the IMR among states in 2017 compared to 1961. In 1961 some of the states had IMR above 120. The government has introduced various measures for reducing IMR in India like Janani Suraksha Yojana, Janani Suraksha Karyakram, measures for protecting the health of mothers, newborn children etc. As a result of these measures and also due to various other socio economic developments such education, employment etc. in India IMR was reduced. In rural area it is still high and needs to be reduced.

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